

CURRENT PROBLEMS OF THE EDUCATION SYSTEM AND ITS DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS IN UKRAINE

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The current conditions of development of the national education system are so changeable that it requires higher and pre-higher education institutions to clearly identify and take into account such changes, as well as to quickly adapt to new conditions. Given the certain conservatism of some of the sciences, especially the fundamental ones, the educational process should be stable, based on well-known postulates and cautiously use not fully defined and proven laws and theorems. On the other hand, advanced majors and specialties in management and administration, including entrepreneurship and trade, marketing, require a greater focus on the use of research results on the behavioral aspects of consumers, competitors, and staff. Thus, certain differences in approaches to the use of methods and models of educational process implementation are not only possible, but also objectively necessary or even mandatory in the field of education. That is, the diversity of existing specialties requires a variety of approaches, a subjective attitude to the principles of the educational process. In our opinion, this situation cannot but raise questions or even some concern among the management of higher education institutions, who traditionally try to average approaches, unify them, define common principles of the educational environment, and this creates stable conditions for contradictions. Such contradictions require finding ways to resolve them, which, in our opinion, is a very relevant area of research [1].

Traditionally, it is believed that the main problems of the national education system are ensuring high quality education in accordance with the demands of the production and non-production sectors of the economy, introduction of innovative technologies, organization of the educational process in difficult conditions, such as during war, etc. And for career development and consolidation of competencies of specialists of the appropriate level of education, only the level of financial support, adaptation of the list and structure of educational components to transformational changes in the socio-economic environment, creation of educational hubs and development of career solutions are necessary and sufficient. In our opinion, the main problem and the main challenge of modern education is the search for effective and rational approaches to the management and organization of the educational process.

A fairly wide range of similar issues was considered in the publications of scholars and educators whose research focuses on the search for directions for reforming the educational sphere and modernizing the educational process. Among domestic and foreign authors, it is necessary to note such as: V. Andrushchenko, N. Pasichnyk, T. Boholit, Y. Pavlenko, and others. The issues of expediency of transformational changes in the educational environment were raised in the works of Yu. Mazur [2], A. Levkina [3], I. Shevchuk [4], O. Bogdanovych, D. Levkina and others. The priority of financial support as the main factor in the development of education for the growth of socio-economic well-being of the population and the development of the state is not new, and at a certain stage we also supported this position [5], as did other researchers.

The full-scale war in Ukraine created barriers to the implementation of the educational process in the traditional form and forced the search for new forms of its organization, taking into account certain results of distance education obtained during the COVID-19 pandemic. The need for rapid modernization and adaptation of the education sector to new realities now took place in the context of the relocation of educational institutions, the change of residence of the majority of the population of the southeastern regions of the country, the de-occupation of the territories of direct hostilities, periodic blackouts, and prolonged air alerts. These conditions had a

significant impact on the organization of distance learning. The old problems that were on the surface during the pandemic have been exacerbated, and now they have received a new vector of influence on the educational sector:

- insufficient financial support for the educational sector and ignoring the needs of domestic educational institutions for ongoing work in the new conditions of military aggression and their strategic needs for functioning in the context of Industry-4.0;

- outdated material and technical base of educational institutions for the implementation of digital educational technologies and the transfer of functional costs to the «shoulders» of research and teaching staff;

- the need to improve the skills of teaching staff in the digitalization of education and the growing stress level of the country's population due to the rapid introduction of digital technologies in all spheres of life and activity;

- the level of remuneration of academic staff that does not correspond to their teaching and research workload and is not equivalent to the corresponding level in other sectors of the economy, including public administration;

- spatial and territorial separation of teachers and students, lack of full communication and psychological contact;

- personal limitations in the use of digital tools due to outdated material and technical support of teachers and students (arising from the moral and technological obsolescence of hardware, software, etc;)

- psychological problems of participants in the distance learning process, which are related to the problems of society as a whole and are reinforced by the personal problems of the affected individuals; arise as a result of adaptation to the language environment (partially can be solved by providing free psychological services and creating appropriate centers, but more often such problems require additional time to perceive the situation and adapt to new conditions).

The intensification of international mobility programs in recent years and the growth of emigration flows in 2022-2023 have created certain problems with the recognition of academic mobility results, double degree diplomas, and in the latter

case, psychological conflict and reluctance to leave the comfort zone after leaving the war zone or occupied territories. Thus, gradually, students and often teachers remain to study or work abroad, which is also a problem and does not ensure stability in society and the educational process. The lack of mechanisms to encourage the return of Ukrainians to domestic institutions, confidence in the quality of education, and motivation to work in enterprises in their specialty after graduation complement the above.

However, the analysis of recent trends still shows that certain traditions regarding the compulsory receipt of higher education or, ultimately, pre-university or vocational education are quite strong. Family traditions, belonging to professional dynasties, continuation of ancestors' professional work, and sometimes public opinion about the possibility of faster career growth and management positions at an enterprise and high salaries continue to play an important role. In 2022, educational institutions worked hard to maintain their own image and the image of higher education, conducted extensive career guidance and took all possible measures to survive. Despite the current problems and uncertainty of the situation for a long period of time, most teachers ensured the educational process, acted in accordance with the orders of the management and depending on the situation in the regions. Thus, school students completed the 2021-2022 academic year prepared for entrance tests, aware of the rules for admission to universities and preferential study conditions. Teachers not only worked in admission committees, they helped volunteers ensure the safety of applicants, organized the work of invincibility points, etc. [2]. Urgent issues still remain unresolved: the organization of quality distance learning in medical and pharmaceutical specialties and specialties related directly or indirectly to life safety, economic security, cybersecurity, international relations, etc., as these require special teaching methods, visualization of processes, development of skills and experience of practical training at enterprises. This leads to a transfer to a foreign educational institution or a longer internship than the terms of the agreement require [4].

However, without attracting financial resources, it is not possible to finally resolve all the problems in the education system and restore the educational process, as most educational institutions have been damaged and destroyed. The assistance of Ukraine's international partners, international organizations (UNESCO, UN, Council of Europe), charitable organizations and private capital is valuable.

The main tasks for the development of education in the nearest future are as follows:

- creating conditions for European integration and internationalization of national education and science;
- close cooperation with business structures to support educational and scientific activities, restore damaged educational institutions;
- ensuring the availability of quality educational services, security of institutions, creating conditions for eliminating the language barrier;
- formation of a unified electronic database on education, widespread use of the latest technologies in the educational process and educational campuses, practical implementation of STEM education and opening of employment centers.

Ukrainian education plays an important role in the development of an independent state, as it provides the necessary knowledge and strengthens intellectual capital, promotes the development of a society with stable moral values [5].

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